

Teacher Performance Review and Evaluation: A Key Lever for Increasing Teacher Quality Time Management

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Abstract. The main objective of conducting this study was to analyze and scrutinize the experiences, evaluate the coping strategies, and assess their insights on teacher performance evaluation and review, focusing on time management. Using the quantitative method of the study, results revealed that two themes were obtained for Figure Three, as described by the Experiences of Teachers on Increasing Time Management. Teachers mentioned and revealed during the interview: Reduced teacher stress and improved teaching skills. The fourth figure also possesses three themes that the teachers grasped as they described the coping strategies, they have developed to manage the said apprehensions on the classroom observation tool as an avenue for activity alignment. First was the openness to teachers' critiques; next was the promotion of teacher development; finally, there was ample time to prepare for the evaluation. Lastly, the educational insight of the teachers on the teacher evaluation was exemplified by three themes drawn and observed during the interview. These were the following: well-prepared teachers enhanced teaching competence and more creativity. It was indeed true that reduced teacher stress and improved teaching skills were among the things that they had chiefly experienced. This primarily connotes that teachers need time management to reduce the stress that they experience. Enhanced teaching competence and more creativity. This theme was a reminder that along with the teaching pedagogy, teachers must be prepared, especially in the delivery of instruction, to ensure the effectiveness, success, and enhancement of the teaching performance and to satisfy the learners with the lesson.

KEY WORDS

1. Time Management 2. teacher evaluation 3. performance review

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1. Introduction

Everything in the teaching field should never settle for less; instead, every aspect of being a teacher should leave room for progress. Teachers must maintain the essence of being creative enough to create something out of nothing, demonstrating how they can cope with every multidimensional change in the field of teaching, as well as an obvious manifestation of the leverage of their instructional process. They should also improve the quality of instruction by clarifying expectations for effective teaching, which will undoubtedly lead to the said continuous professional development. The ongoing appearance of new learning tools and educational technology puts much pressure on teachers and encourages them to create innovative and ef-

fective techniques for continuous professional development in order to improve the quality of learning outcomes and self-efficacy. Otherwise, this explains why teaching is lifetime learning. One of the benefits of teaching is the ability to experiment with new ideas and methods of instruction as we try to suit the requirements of a constantly changing set of students. Unfortunately, instructors are not perfect, even if they have excellent intentions and do their best to accomplish their duties. The philosophy of performance evaluation states that the evaluation process exists to facilitate the improvement of instruction. The evaluation procedures and associated instruments provide the framework for assessing teacher performance related to the adopted performance criteria. According to Halim et al. (2018), teacher performance review and evaluation is the action of assessing another teacher's class performance, learning, and reflecting. It is also a method of assessing and capturing specific information about what is happening in the classroom. Through teacher performance review and evaluation, teachers are regularly exposed to fresh teaching practices that they may not have explored previously. This reaffirmed and showed that teacher evaluation can be utilized as a guide for teachers to reflect on their teaching approaches. At the same time, those observing can learn about the methods of others, perhaps more successful educators. Although charts, rating scales, checklists, and narrative descriptions have been used to analyze effective teaching, systematic teacher performance evaluation based on interactive coding systems has been the most extensively utilized process or research approach. Martinez (2011) stated, as referenced by Zaare (2012). Furthermore, Gall and Acheson (2011) state that one stage in identifying adjustments teachers might want to make is evaluating them. Evaluators could be peers, other instructors with more skill and experience, supervisors, principals, or government officials. Evaluators can take notes on the lesson using observation tools, checklists, or rubrics, according to Joyce and Showers (2002). In teacher evaluation, O'Leary (2013) explores the relevance of lesson observation in the training, assessment, and growth of new and seasoned instructors. The focus on the teacher's point of view ensures that the teacher watches and evaluates his or her own performance. It enables teachers to constantly and continuously reflect on their own classroom discourse, resulting in increased awareness. This simply means that teacher evaluation is a driving tool for every teacher because it provides feedback based on the said classroom observations, and it can help teachers in their continuing professional development. Meanwhile, in the United States of America, Malu (2015) noted in her paper "Observation Tools for Professional Development" that it is also critical to have opportunities to implement improvements in teaching. Teachers may experiment with changing instruction using a small group of students and an observer. It is also crucial to have opportunities to implement changes in teaching. Teachers may experiment with changing instruction using a small group of students and an observer. Professional development benefits instructors, including English language teachers, since it allows them to make adjustments that improve teaching and learning. Murray (2010) and Gall and Acheson (2011). Joyce and Showers (2002) also identified crucial characteristics that support teacher change in their seminal research on staff development and professional development in today's terms. Observation, feedback, and practice are three of these aspects. In addition, as Bruns et al. One favorable implication of the Latin America research is the potential for increased school-level performance gains through greater diffusion of best teaching practices within schools, similar to how the exchange of practice among teachers in a school is a core strategy in high-performing East Asian systems like Japan's lesson study, Singapore, and Shanghai. Teacher performance

evaluation is used to do all of this. Teacher performance review and evaluation were adopted in the Philippines, notably in Cavite. It was successful in its initial attempt to implement this approach. However, the evaluators may improve in certain areas, such as offering a more personalized post-conference with the faculty member engaged, coordination between the observer and the faculty, and the manner in which the observer offered comments. In addition, teacher evaluation is part of faculty professional development and requirements in the Philippines' higher education. This is one method of addressing staff or student academic concerns through observations. It is never too late for educators to change how they teach in the classroom. We must examine our teaching to see if there are any areas where we are not reacting as well as we should. We can ask a friend, colleague, or fellow teacher to assist us in identifying aspects of our teaching that we want to improve. Teacher performance evaluation is essential in this case. Thus, in Division of Digos City, notably at Aplaya Elementary School, the researcher emphasized the importance of teacher performance evaluation and review as critical at all stages of a teacher's career. Furthermore, even experienced teachers are not always aware of the nature of their interactions with specific students. One of the most essential goals of teacher evaluation is to help teachers improve their classroom instruction. Through feedback, teachers can gain awareness of how their classroom runs and make desired changes. Teachers must also recognize their strengths and limitations to enhance their instruction. Teaching is at the center of what educational institutions do, and we should always search for ways to improve what we do as professionals. Teachers are accountable for their professional development, and teacher evaluation can help your institution enhance the quality of teaching and management in its education. Some academics contend that the definition and measurement of effective teaching are vague and subjective. Others feel that evaluating good teaching is attainable provided goals, expectations, and criteria have been properly articulated and established.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The main objective in conducting this study, the educational possibilities towards the synergy of continuous professional development of the teachers using analyzing their experience, the advantages and the disadvantages as well as their insights on teacher performance evaluation and review. The above-mentioned experiences of teachers are the ultimate feature as a way of feedback after evaluations that help teachers reflect on what worked, what did not work, and what they might modify is another important element in the teacher change process. This also aims to solidify the professional development of the teachers primarily on the teaching and learning processes, as this practice aims to empower and promote teacher change, how might teachers engage in this process to make changes in their teaching.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intended to gain insight into the experiences of teachers who have performed performance evaluations and reviews as tools for the synergy of their continuous professional development. These experiences were beneficial to generate improvement in their teaching strategies and to proceed on empowered instructional processes. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the teachers' experiences on the teacher increasing time management?
- (2) How do teachers cope with challenges in acquiring teacher performance evaluation and review, increasing time management?
- (3) What educational insights can be drawn from the study findings?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Teacher Performance Evaluation – A systematic process used to assess the effectiveness, competence, and professional growth of teachers based on specific criteria, including time management and instructional delivery.

Time Management – The ability of teachers to plan and control their time effectively to balance instructional responsibilities, preparation, and other teaching-related tasks, ultimately reducing stress and improving performance.

Coping Strategies – The adaptive techniques and approaches employed by teachers to handle stress and challenges related to performance evaluation, including openness to critiques, teacher development, and preparation for assessments.

Classroom Observation Tool – An evaluation instrument used to assess teaching performance, align activities with learning objectives, and provide feedback for professional improvement.

Teacher Stress – The emotional and psychological pressure experienced by educators due to workload, performance assessments, and time constraints, which can impact teaching effectiveness.

Teaching Competence – The ability of teachers to deliver lessons effectively, engage students, and utilize instructional strategies that enhance learning outcomes.

Creativity in Teaching – The capacity of teachers to develop innovative and engaging instructional methods that enhance student participation and understanding.

Pedagogy – The methods and practices used in teaching, including instructional strategies, classroom management, and lesson planning, to facilitate effective learning.

Educational Insights – The key realizations and reflections of teachers regarding their experiences with performance evaluation, time management, and professional growth.

Activity Alignment – The process of ensuring that teaching activities, lesson plans, and assessments are aligned with learning objectives to improve student outcomes and teacher effectiveness.

1.4. Significant of the Study—Within the preview of this study, it focuses on the beneficiary of the following: The Department of Education would provide teachers with varied opportunities to unlock educational possibilities and continuously grow in their profession by offering equipped training, workshops, seminars, and other essential programs that would ensure their welfare. The teachers should effectively build a solid foundation for their profession, continuously grow, and enhance and practice their teaching skillset to achieve improved teaching performances by means of acquiring a skillset from teacher performance evaluation and review. Lastly, the findings of this study would enable future researchers to facilitate research that involves teacher performance evaluation, helping teachers improve their teaching and management. This study would also serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The review of this research is anchored on the existing theoretical framework that can help shape the way researchers conceptualize this study, which is entitled the educational possibilities towards the synergy of continuous professional development of teachers through the lens of the classroom observation tool. The selected research theories each contribute to our understanding of how environmental factors influence young children's experiences within their families. This study highlighted the Systematic Observation

and Analysis of Teaching of Burton, (1969), which this document essentially contains recommendations for the construction of in-service education programs to train school staff members in the use of observational systems, as well as a list of possible applications for such systems. Observation systems are being more widely used worldwide for various goals, including understanding and improving instruction. Individual observation systems differ significantly. Furthermore, the researchers also used Kolb's experiential learning, which entails reconstructing one's experiences through observation, analysis of feedback, appraisal of skills, attitudes, and knowledge, and exploration of new professional possibilities according to Schon, (1983) as cited by Donnely (2010). Moreover, this also upholds theories in education as described by Tatto (1999) which states that the behavioristic approach which states that the teacher education is seen as mastering a set of skills to support teachers in the performance of a predetermined task, second is the humanistic teacher education, which is related to adult development where teachers are encouraged to find their own best ways to function as teachers, third is teaching as a craft, where teaching is accumulated by trial and error and is to be found in the wisdom of the experienced practitioners. A master- apprentice relationship is seen as necessary to uncover good practice and pass it on to the novice, and lastly, inquiry-oriented teacher education emphasizes the development of inquiry about teaching and the contexts in which teaching is carried out. The focus is on helping teachers develop dispositions and skills of critical inquiry to analyze what they are doing about its influence upon learners, schools, and the larger society. This research delved into scrutinizing and influential teachers' experiences in performing the classroom observational tool, as this tool is said to benchmark for teachers in engaging and empowering their instructional process through classroom observations. Moreover, this also serves as an immediate response to those modifications that every teacher must acquire to improve their effectiveness, particularly in the instructional process, as well as to promote life-long learning and continuous professional development. In this study, the Venn Diagram shown in the study exemplifies the connectivity between teachers' experiences, the advantages and disadvantages of classroom observation tool and finally the statements that in need to address by the participants of the study to improve their teaching efficacy.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the research design, research participant, philosophical assumptions, research instrument, trustworthiness of the study, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study data collection and the ethical consideration. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—Philosophy is being defined as the use of abstract ideas and beliefs that inform the research. Philosophical assumptions are typically the first ideas in developing a study, but how they relate to the overall process of research remains a mystery stated by Lynham and Lincoln (2011). The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It established the background used for the following conclusions and decisions. An understanding of the philosophical assumptions behind qualitative research begins with assessing where it fits within

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

the overall process of research, noting its importance as an element of research, and considering how to actively write it into a study. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types will be elaborated below. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln as cited by Creswell (2012) state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being the researchers he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an insider, thus the researcher assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Moreover, conducting a qualitative study means that researchers try to get as close as possible to the participants being studied and this basically

revolves around with the epistemological assumption. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. Hence, to conduct studies in the place where the participants live and work is very important as for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the place or get to know the participants, the more they know what they know from firsthand information. In short, the researcher tries to minimize the distance between himself or herself and those being researched. Thus, Epistemological assumption is known to be how researchers know what they know as they try to get as close as possible to participants being studied. Subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views from research conducted in the field. Ontology also called as the nature of reality is primarily related to the nature of reality and its characteristics. Researchers embrace the idea of multiple realities and report on these multiple realities by exploring multiple forms of evidence from

different individuals' perspectives and experiences. Thus, this part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), the reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994). In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The researcher underpinned the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. He or she therefore, preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric means that reporting what reality was through the eyes of my research participants. This was important because it means that the researcher would report objectively on what was observed and

of responses. The researcher also made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result and upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progresses. Axiology on the other hand refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discussed values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Researchers make their values known in the study and actively reports their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. All researchers bring values to a study, but qualitative researchers make their values known in a study. This is the axiological assumption that characterizes qualitative research. In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. The researcher's presence is apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989, as cited by Carnaghan, 2019)

heard from the participants. The researcher also used personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity. Patton (2000) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the questions on the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people. The goal of this research study worked well with this definition in trying to understand school heads experience and others involved in the community collaboration to eliminate them or lessen the misallocation of school support

financial need particularly in the operating expenses or mandatory expenses are more useful and meaningful. Guba (2007) pointed out that the researcher needs to prepare for an investigation that greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. The author also suggested that information was viewed as only as the tip of the iceberg. The researcher implemented the qualitative research method of phenomenology to allow for exploration of the school heads experience and others involved in the school community to eliminate them or lessen the misallocation of school support financial need particularly in the operating expenses or mandatory expenses are more useful and meaningful and revealed their feelings and idea towards these experiences. Burns and Grove (2003) stated that phenomenology is a philosophy, an approach or perspective to living, learning and doing research. The phenomenological research's goal was to capture the lived experiences, to find meaning that may or may not be known to the person who experienced it, and to describe the phenomenon through the composite narrative. For the qualitative researcher, the only reality was the reality participants in-

involved in the research situations constructed. Carnaghan, (2019) finally highlighted that it is a very vital factor that the philosophical assumptions which underlies qualitative research and to be able to articulate them in a research study is understood. It is helpful in articulating the importance of philosophy in research because It shapes how we formulate our problem and research questions to study and how we seek information to answer the questions, next is the assumptions are deeply rooted in our training and reinforced by the scholarly community in which we work. This raises the question as to whether key assumptions can change and whether multiple philosophical assumptions can be used in a given study. Whether multiple assumptions can be taken in a given study it may be related to research experiences of the investigator, his or her openness to exploring using differing assumptions, and the acceptability of ideas taken in the larger scientific community of which he or she is a part. On the reverse side, understanding the differences used by a reviewer may enable an author-researcher to resolve points of difference before they become a focal point for critique.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—A qualitative research method was utilized in this study, employing a phenomenological qualitative design. Phenomenological research deals with the study of experiences from the standpoint of different individual as well as considering those taken-for-granted viewpoints and their usual ways of perceiving. It is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasizes the importance of the individual perspective. Thus, this research design was a powerful method for understanding subjective experiences and gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions. Qualitative research methods were also considered to describe life experiences and give them meaning as a sys-

tematic subjective approach. To gain insight, explore the depth, richness, and complexity inherent in the phenomenon. It was primarily described as soft science, focuses on complex broad perspectives, holistic, subjective, dialectic, inductive reasoning, basis of knowing is mainly on meaning discovery, develops theory, shared interpretation, communication observation, fundamental element of analysis is on words. To describe experiences as they are lived, qualitative research examines uniqueness of individual's lived situations since each person has own reality; reality was subjective while according to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews were provided

in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and helped grasp the subjects' perspective. Agreeing to Creswell, (2013) as cited by Chambers (2013), on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group, phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research. To describe the nature of the specific phenomenon serves as the principal aim of this kind of research approach. Typically, interviews are conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data such as documents, observations and art may also be used. The data is then read, reread, and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning. Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience, and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. The qualitative research explored and described the experiences of teachers and others involved in the community. The research technique used was a modified van Kaam method described by Moustakas (2000) based on recorded and transcribed interviews using semi-structured questions to capture the teachers' experience. Qualitative research design was a research method used extensively by scientists and researchers studying human behavior, opinions, themes, and motivations. It was said to be the oldest of all techniques, where the ancient Greek philosophers qualitatively observed the world around them and tried to understand and explain what they saw. While qualitative methods are sometimes assumed to be easier than other methods of research, the information provided by the conduct of qualitative research provides a depth of understanding about phenomena that cannot be achieved in other ways. Added to, Shuttleworth, and Wilson, (2008) stated that probably the most flexible type of research design is the qualitative research is among the various experimental techniques, encompassing a variety of accepted methods and structures considering its usefulness when a pain hypothesis was utilized in a more complex and broad subject and at the same time yields data that is richer and more insightful into underlying reasons and patterns within phenomena. More importantly, this research was more practical when budgets were small and sample sizes were restricted, as a few available participants could be better understood through in-depth interviews. The benefit of qualitative research is that it can paint a picture of a phenomenon that might be hidden with a more dispassionate quantitative review. On the other hand, phenomenological research seeks to tend to such matters of existence as this to reunite the critical illness survivor with their original world. It tends to unhide things of existence, such as facets of awareness like intuition and feeling, which can often be overlooked. These things can only be realized through phenomenological awareness. Phenomenology unveils original experience and its meaning. In so doing, phenomenology offers a more profound understanding that can bring about individuals' perception of a specific topic. Phenomenology foregrounds human experience and brings a holistic approach to human treatment. This research inquiry seeks to understand human experience from an individual's perspective in contrast to the objectifying and reductionist nature of empiricist research methods (Tembo, 2016). Moreover, Qutoshi, S. (2018), phenomenology as a philosophy and a method of inquiry is not limited to an approach to knowing, it was instead an intellectual engagement in interpretations and meaning making that is used to understand the lived world of human beings at a conscious level. Historically, it was a science of understanding human beings at a deeper level by gazing at the phenomenon. Using this approach, a researcher uses bracketing as a taken-for-granted assumption in describing the natural appearance of phenomena to gain insights into lived experiences and interpret for meaning making. The data

collection and analysis take place side by side to illuminate the specific expertise to identify the phenomena that are perceived by the actors in a particular situation. The outcomes of a phenomenological study broaden the mind, improve the ways of thinking to see a phenomenon, and enable researchers to see ahead and define their posture through intentional study of lived experiences. However, the subjectivity and personal knowledge in perceiving and interpreting it from the research participant's point of view has been central in phenomenological studies. To achieve such an objective, phenomenology could be used extensively in social sciences. Conversely, several challenges were pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected in the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his/her own experiences and observations, which is difficult to do. The researcher needs to decide how and when his/her observations were incorporated into the study. Advantages associated with phenomenology include a better understanding of meanings attached by people and its contribution to developing new theories. Its disadvantages include difficulties with analysis and interpretation, usually lower levels of validity and reliability compared to positivism, and more time and other

resources required for data collection (Hycner, 2008). Similarly, Schutz, (2010) stressed that the purpose of the phenomenological approach was to illuminate the specific, to identify phenomena through how the actors perceive them in a situation. In the human sphere, this typically translates into gathering 'deep' information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions and participant observation, and representing it from the research participant's perspective. Phenomenology is concerned with the study of experience from the individual's perspective, 'bracketing' taken-for-granted assumptions and usual ways of perceiving. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, emphasizing the importance of individual perspective and interpretation. As such, they were dominant for understanding the subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study is to explore and assess the teachers' apprehension about classroom observation as a tool inside the classroom, particularly in activity augment, the researcher intended to employ phenomenology as a type of qualitative method.

2.4. Research Participants—This study focuses on the analysis of the teachers' experiences with classroom observation tools as a key feature towards the synergy of the continuous professional development of the teachers, as well as ultimately gauges the teachers' teaching effectiveness in delivering the instructional process. The researcher collected data from ten (10) public elementary teachers assigned at the five (5) Laak South District, Division of Davao de Oro schools. Furthermore, the researcher chose two (2) informants from the schools who are

said to be the beginning teachers with at least three to five years of teaching service and experience being observed in the classroom. The researcher desired an extensive gathering of ideas from the key informants. This research also chose purposive sampling to certify that the informants are reliable and knowledgeable and possess much experience in the research topic. Further, purposive sampling also guaranteed the quality of data to be collected and adequate information; thus, purposive sampling was used in this study. To protect against bias and pro-

vide a permanent record of what was being said and not said, all interviews were tape-recorded and transcribed verbatim afterwards. To help in data analysis, thoughts and ideas about the interview also helped make field notes about the observation during and immediately after each interview. A good quality multi-directional external microphone was used to record focus

groups, as internal microphones help cope with the variation in volume of different speakers. If observers present, they were introduced to the participants as someone just there to observe and often took notes. Videotaping requires more than one camera to capture the whole group and additional operational personnel in the room (Chadwick, et. al., 2008).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were vital to the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant groups addressed in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most critical parts of the research. The researcher needed to promote the aims of the research, imparting factual knowledge, truth, and prevention of error.

Social Value

Research was essential to society. In this study, the social value focused on the experience of teachers in handling fast learners, as this study was conducted explicitly among the elementary. Thus, the social problem that pushes the researcher's interest is the challenges the teachers face towards the teachers' experience and others involved in the community collaboration to eliminate them or lessen the problem of drop out in the schools, whether their strategies or program were good enough. This study could serve as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions that benefit classroom teachers.

Informed Consent

Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pellerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a

signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness-to-participate-in-the-study release. The informed consent letter aims to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and identify the anticipated information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating.

INFORMED CONSENT AND VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

The process of obtaining Consent consists of the following: consent should be given freely (voluntary), subjects should understand what is being asked of them, and involved persons must be competent to consent (2). This means, to participate in a research study, participants need to be adequately informed about the research, comprehend the information and have a power of freedom of choice to allow them to decide

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lowing: consent should be given voluntarily, subjects shall understand the questions, and the persons involved must be competent to consent. Thus, to participate in a research study, participants need to be adequately informed about the research, comprehend the information, and have a power of freedom of choice to decide whether to participate or decline, and all participants were required to provide written informed consent. The potential participants were approached one by one, and the purpose of the study and the data collection process were explained to them. They were given an appropriate time to ask questions and address any concerns. It was explained that as their participation was voluntary, refusing to participate in the study while it was in progress would not affect their care. At the same time, a participant's information sheet was provided to explain the study further. The potential participants were given appropriate time (in this case: 24 hours up to one week) to read the information sheet and decide whether they wanted to be involved in this study. They were required to sign the informed consent form before the interview to indicate their permission to be part of the study, and this signature was confirmed before the interview session. Arifin, (2018) also added. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to participate was ensured to be entirely voluntary in nature and based on an understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection are described in the appendices of this study.

Vulnerability Of Research Participants

Acknowledging and addressing the vulnerability of research participants was crucial for ethical research practices. Researchers must balance scientific exploration and safeguard participants' rights and well-being, particularly those at greater risk of harm or exploitation. Researchers can achieve more respectful and

impactful research outcomes by adopting ethical approaches and actively involving vulnerable populations. The study participants were deemed capable of answering the research instrument because they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that the researcher was easily reached through contact number and address in case there were some clarifications or questions about the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety

The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members if they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer the possible questions of the respondents. Furthermore, if respondents experience possible discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher was also ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a secure venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, as well as risk minimization. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherited from this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Privacy

This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data could not be traced back to their actual sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed outputs that were carried out from this study were kept anonymous. Furthermore, all the issues were considered to avoid conflict of interest among the researcher and

the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided.

Anonymity and Confidentiality

The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identities in the data collection, analysis, and reporting of the study findings. The privacy and confidentiality of the interview environment were also managed carefully during telephone communication, interview sessions, data analysis, and dissemination of the findings. Justice During data gathering, the respondents were informed of my role and their corresponding role. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any communication about the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study's results.

Transparency

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher applied qualitative analysis to establish the study's credibility, transferability, and dependability. The participants' experiences were collected and investigated using one-on-one, non-structured, audio-taped interviews, field notes, and peer debriefing. The audio tape one-on-one, structured interview, peer debriefing, and field notes was performed by participants within 4 days, with each session lasting between 1 hour and 15 minutes. Interview Guide. To gather additional information and supporting answers to validate the study's findings, the researcher prepared five open-ended questions in the unstructured interview. The interview questions were inclined to the components contained in the questionnaire. Unstructured interviews did not reflect preconceived theories or ideas and were performed with little or no organization. Their usage was generally only with significant depth, or virtually nothing is known

The results of the study can be accessed by the respondents, heads of the participating schools, because the information is available, and was placed in a CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher to provide. Also, by learning from the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the research and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can request to be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

about the subject area, or a different perspective of a known subject area is required. The research interview explores individuals' views, experiences, beliefs, and motivations on specific matters. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, are believed to provide a deeper understanding of social phenomena than would be obtained from purely quantitative methods, such as questionnaires (Stewart et. al., 2008) A questionnaire was set up with carefully designed, written down, and tested questions asked of individual respondents to gather information in a research study (Enon, 2008). The questionnaires were also an appropriate way to quickly collect large amounts of data. The open-ended questions allowed the respondents to provide further opinions by qualifying or substantiating their answers. They were intended to tap as much information as possible from the different categories of respondents. O'Leary (2014) added that questionnaires are used most notably

to discover what the masses think. These include market research, political polling, customer service feedback, evaluations, opinion polls, and social science research.

2.7. Data Collection—The researcher then collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via lengthy interviews. Next, the data analysis involved horizontalization, which extracted significant statements from transcribed interviews. The critical statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each would fall under specific psycholog-

2.8. Data Analysis—In gathering information, the researcher would personally conduct in-depth interviews with participants and saturate the information through one-on-one interviews. Interviewing refers to structured or unstructured verbal communication between the researcher and the participants. The interview was conducted in a conducive, quiet environment, meaning free from disturbance, and that the participants feel safe in the environment. The interview was initiated individually for about 30 to 40 minutes. In the light of the principles of decorum and standards, the researcher adheres to the following steps in the conduct of interview and focus group discussion and that is first make an appointment with the participants, second prepare a quiet room conducive to conversation, third is to arrange chairs to enhance a face-to-face interviewing, next is to prepared a voice recorder, and lastly, to provide a jar of water. Before conducting the interview, the researcher would thank the participants for their time and willingness to participate in the study. The researcher would remind the participants of the agreement, explain that the interview would be unstructured, and that the information given would determine probing questions. The researcher secured the permission of the partic-

ical and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textual description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his/her meaning of the experience here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience.

ipants to record the interview (Talbot, 2005). Furthermore, Interviews also have strengths and weaknesses. The strength of an interview is that it provides valuable information when participants cannot be directly observed. The interviewer has better control over the types of information that they receive. They can also pick their questions. If worded effectively, questions encourage unbiased and truthful answers. However, the weaknesses include that the interviewee may provide biased information or be unreliable if only one interviewer interprets the data. The best research requires many different points of view. The answers may be deceptive because the interviewee tries to respond in a way that pleases the interviewer. Then, equipment may be costly and require high technical competence. It can be time-consuming and inexperienced interviewers may be unable to keep the questions suitably focused (Quad, 2016). The researcher would also stimulate conversations and reactions through the focus group discussion since focus groups may share many standard features with less structured interviews. However, there is more to them than merely collecting similar data from many participants at once. A focus group is a group discussion on a particular topic organized for research purposes

(Chadwick et al., 2008). Furthermore, in the study, the researcher guarantees the safety of the respondents when gathering the data. This is to ensure that the process under this study is safe from the pandemic, COVID-19, thus the researcher adheres to the protocol given by the Philippine government under the Department of Education and the Department of Health with the alignment from the World Health Organization and the Inter-Agency Task Force Against Emerging Diseases. On May 8, 2020, the IATF Meeting the Department of Education secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones presented the highlights of the draft Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), and the DepEd's decision on the date of the school opening for SY 2020-2021 including all the guidelines and protocols that should be followed for the safety and security of all the administrators, teachers, students as well as the stakeholder amidst this global pandemic. Also, the World Health Organization highlighted measures to follow. Dur-

ing this research, the researcher must secure a fully clean and disinfected classroom where the respondents would answer the questionnaire. Upon entering the classroom, the respondents must frequently wash their hands with soap and safe water. If soap and water are not readily available, use an alcohol-based hand sanitizer with at least 60% alcohol. Added to, inside the classroom, physical distancing should be emphasized of at least 1 meter between individuals including spacing of desks, frequent hand and respiratory hygiene, age-appropriate mask use, ventilation and environmental cleaning measures should be in place to limit exposure and finally, the researcher should enforce the policy of staying home if the respondents are not feeling well. Likewise, the researcher may also conduct the survey virtually using Zoom, Google Meet, Google Forms, and Facebook Messenger to ensure that everyone is safe and is not at risk during the study.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—It was shown in the analytical framework that the teachers' experiences in their apprehensions on the classroom observation tool, as this helped them improve the teaching pedagogy, bring a new perspective on how to cope with the challenges that the teachers encounter during the classroom observations. The experiences were analyzed to identify their perceptions and feelings and make a difference in the educational system. The data collected during interviews were transcribed, organized, and reviewed for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Figure 2 shows procedures undertaken to analyze the textual data. Collected transcripts were listened to and transcribed with a list of significant statements that would be developed from them and

grouped into larger units of information called "meaning tunings" or themes (Creswell, 2007). With the list of non-redundant units of meaning, the researcher must continue to bracket any assumptions to remain faithful to the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004). The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. Clusters of themes are typically formed by grouping units of meaning (Creswell, 1998). Moustakas (1984) described writing a description. Next, a structural description was written about the experience, reflecting on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced (Creswell, 2007). Finally, a composite description of the phenomenon was written; this is the essence of the experience and represents the culmination of the phenomenological study (Creswell, 2007).

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Qualitative content analysis was commonly used to analyze qualitative data. However, few articles have examined the trustworthiness of its use in nursing science studies. Qualitative content analysis's trustworthiness is often presented using credibility, dependability, conformability, transferability, and authenticity. This article focuses on trustworthiness based on a review of previous studies, our own experiences, and methodological textbooks. Trustworthiness is described for the main qualitative content analysis phases, from data collection to reporting results. The researcher concluded that it was vital to scrutinize the trustworthiness of every phase of the analysis process, including the preparation, organization, and reporting of results. Together, these phases should give a reader a clear indication of the overall trustworthiness of the study. The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the issue of credibility, interview as many research participants as possible, or up to the point of saturation. Moreover, in qualitative studies, it was pertinent to address how qualitative researchers establish that the research study's findings are credible, transferable, confirmable, and dependable. Trustworthiness was all about establishing these four things, which are described in more detail below. Transferability. Qualitative research refers to how the researcher illustrates

that the findings of their study are relevant to other contexts. This can include comparable situations, populations, or phenomena. To establish transferability, qualitative researchers often employ thick description, which provides detailed accounts that allow readers to assess the applicability of the findings to their contexts, circumstances, and situations. Dependability in research refers to the degree to which other researchers can replicate a study, yielding consistent outcomes. Someone who seeks to replicate your study should find sufficient information in your research report and arrive at similar results. An inquiry audit can be employed to enhance dependability in qualitative research. This involves having an external reviewer assess and scrutinize the research process and data analysis, ensuring that the findings were consistent and that the study could be replicated. Credibility. Researcher credibility refers to the degree of confidence a qualitative researcher has in the authenticity of the study's findings. Essentially, it revolves around the truth and accuracy of those findings. To enhance the credibility of their research, qualitative researchers can employ triangulation, which helps to substantiate the validity of the study's results. Confirmability refers to the extent to which a research study's findings remain objective and unbiased. It indicates that the results are grounded in the participants' responses rather than influenced by the researcher's biases or motivations. To ensure confirmability, qualitative researchers can create an audit trail detailing each data analysis stage, explaining the rationale behind their decisions. This allows for a more explicit demonstration that the study's results genuinely reflect the participants' perspectives.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the thematic analysis of the interview data. It presents themes that emerge from the analysis. Along with the themes are figures and comprehensive discussions that answer the study's objectives. This chapter discusses the themes that

emerged from the data gathered. The result primarily presented the description and background of the participants who assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. The Teachers' Apprehension On The Classroom Observation Tool (COT)—Based on the interview data gathered, the participants' experiences on the time management as a benchmark to the improved teaching and increasing teaching skills. As the researchers, one of the teachers' experiences highlighted in the interview is the improved teaching performance. Teachers are indeed suppressed by the dilemma of the decline of teaching performance, which leads to the poor performance of the students and the weak institutional organization. Thus, it is indeed a factor that the teachers should engage more in teacher evaluations, as this will provide the teachers with the modification of their teaching skills, which will later be the outlet towards improved teaching skills. Time management is one way to enhance the instructional process of the teachers, as this will provide them an enlightenment as to where they need to enhance their teaching abilities.

3.1.1. Improved Teaching Skills—Improving teaching and learning is always paramount to a good school; teacher activity is the key to excellence in education. To ensure a continuous improvement in teaching and learning, classroom observation has always been used. As mentioned, the performance of pupils and school instructors is directly correlated with the impact of teachers' time management. Teachers engaging in proactive and thoughtful planning can generate more knowledgeable thoughts for the country's future growth. The noteworthy connection between educators' time management and pupils' academic achievement was discovered. The degree of educational attainment and time management among instructors was moderate, thus it was advised that educators enhance their time management abilities via awareness of managing their schedule (Kayode, Ayodele, 2015). Based on the results, it is clear that through controlled feedback on instructional methods, classroom observation tools are an invaluable resource for enhancing teaching abilities. They promote a reflective approach to teaching by giving teachers insights on their areas of strength and growth. These tools assist educators in coordinating their approaches with best practices and learning objectives by providing explicit criteria and performance indicators. Frequent observations foster mentorship and peer collaboration, which promotes the sharing of successful tactics. In the end, these resources foster a culture of ongoing development, which improves student outcomes and instructional quality. Teachers' stress is one of the many things the participants wanted everyone to acknowledge as they engaged in the classroom observation tool. They highlighted their long and sleepless nights preparing for the classroom observations, such as the pertinent papers, visual aids, and themselves. It is indeed evident that the bottom line of this result is that teachers who are proficient in time management can drastically lower their stress levels by learning how to prioritize their responsibilities and effectively handle their workload. By managing their time well, teachers can reduce feelings of overload by allocating enough time for class planning, grading, and administrative tasks. Teachers can maintain a better work-life balance and reduce stress by planning their schedule and setting realistic goals. Teachers' efforts are rewarded when they can concentrate on high-impact activities that directly promote students' learning thanks to these skills. Teachers are therefore more satisfied with their jobs and are less likely to burn out.

Fig. 3. Experiences Of Teachers On The Increasing Time Management

3.1.2. *Reduced Teacher Stress*—Working as a public-school teacher is a great challenge. There is much work to be done and accomplished. Doing paperwork is just one thing, providing quality learning is another. Time management throughout a teacher’s career, whether part of supervision or routine administrative monitoring, must know how to manage time. Gleeson, K., (2004) stated that teachers aim to get their students involved in worthwhile learning activities is one of the common goals. Your learners are working on suitable and meaningful assignments throughout this time. Your students will learn more the more productively you can teach them. At least 27 of the school day is spent on non-instructional activities such as lunch, breaks, downtime in between ses-

sions, switching classrooms, and other distractions. In numerous classrooms, that percentage rises above 40This corroborates Roberts Dyer, (2004), showing time management techniques. lessen your tension. Less job-induced stress was associated with the teachers’ perception of control over their time. This suggests that teachers could handle the demands of teaching agriculture better using time management techniques more frequently. This additional research adds credence to the advantages of using time management techniques with aspiring educators. This suggests that teachers were more adept at managing the demands of their jobs when they used time management techniques more frequently. This study adds to the evidence demonstrating the advantages of teaching future educators time management skills.

3.2. *Teachers Cope Up With Challenges In Acquiring Teacher Performance Evaluation and Review Increasing Time Management*—In this research question, the respondents were try-

ing to cope with the challenges in acquiring teacher performance evaluation and review, and increasing time management. To summarize, based on the information given by the infor-

ments, it is very clear that teachers highlighted open-mindedness when the classroom observation tool is encountered. Teacher evaluation tool provides the teachers with evaluation from the mentors or highly experienced teachers, as they

will be throwing criticism and suggestions on your performance. To withstand criticisms and to be able to improve oneself, being open to any suggestions and making criticism constructive are the ways to improve successfully.

3.2.1. Openness for Critiques—Open-mindedness allows for creative insights that can go beyond what you already know and enables productive collaboration with others. Open-mindedness is one of the fundamental aims of education. It is considered an attitude of wonder, interest in new ideas, and determination to have one's beliefs adequately grounded. It is vitally important because we live in a world of constant change. Thus, this indicates that Professional development is fostered in a climate that supports openness to criticism in teacher performance reviews and evaluations. Establishing a transparent culture makes teachers more open to receiving constructive criticism and see it as a chance for growth rather than condemnation. Teachers can better understand the precise areas where they may improve their methods when there is clear communication during evaluations. This transparency fosters a cooperative conversation that builds mutual trust and understanding between educators and assessors. Additionally, it allows educators to take charge of their development by setting individualized goals. In the end, highlighting constructive criticism in assessments results in a more motivated and engaged teaching staff, which is advantageous for teachers and students. Additionally, to

help new teachers become better instructors like them, mentors and critical teachers must continue to be sincere and committed to the cause. Promising instructors should be encouraged not only for their positive traits and proficiency with instructional strategies, but also to ensure they pass the teacher license exam. However, new teachers must learn from students' feedback, their own teaching methods, and criticism of their traits. They must also be taught that obtaining a license and passing the teacher licensure exam guarantees they can practice teaching (Ramos and Crescini, 2020). The above statements exhibit the respondents' arguments regarding the development of the teachers as they employ the teacher evaluation tool in their practice. This emphasizes that teacher performance in the teaching and learning process can be developed and enhanced through a teacher evaluation system portrayed primarily on the classroom observation tool. This also extends to the mentoring of highly experienced teachers as they provide suggestions, recommendations, and constructive criticism of a particular teacher on how they exemplify the instructional process. Thus, this Teacher evaluation tool serves as a platform for improving teachers' performance and continually developing the teaching pedagogy.

3.2.2. Highly Effective Teaching Practice—Classroom observation plays a central role in making teaching and learning more visible. It provides teachers constructive critical feedback to improve classroom management and instructional techniques. Teachers need to observe the

interaction between the teacher and the learner within the classroom because it can determine the learning opportunities students get. Not only that, but classroom observation also encourages colleagues to collaborate to improve teacher practice and student learning. Feedback

from classroom observations is an effective way to provide teachers with the information they need about their classroom behavior, and it can help them in their continuous professional development (CPD). This is anchored in Gordon et al. (2006), who state that teacher effectiveness is a gauge of job success in the teaching profession since it may quantify a teacher's influence while carrying out their duties. According to John et al. (2008), those with high conscientiousness are typically very responsible, achievement-focused, and organized. In most meta-analyses, conscientiousness has been the best predictor of job performance since these characteristics enable one to complete a task successfully. The factors most positively correlated with job success include, in particular, the ability to start and finish tasks, the motivation to attain goals, and moral consciousness. Teacher preparation was also one of the coping mechanisms of the teachers on the classroom observation tool, as they stated primarily

that they experience teacher stress and burnout. Through ample preparation, teachers successfully managed to use the classroom observation tool. In summary, teacher performance reports and evaluations must be well-prepared and given enough time to guarantee fairness and accuracy. To thoroughly assess a teacher's performance, evaluators require time to compile pertinent information, including lesson plans, student feedback, and observations made in the classroom. Teachers gain from taking the time to evaluate their methods, compile a record of their successes, and identify areas for improvement. This planning facilitates thoughtful conversations throughout the review process, leading to a more accurate and helpful assessment. When both sides are ready, the conversation may concentrate more effectively on professional growth. In the end, having enough time to prepare guarantees that the evaluation process is viewed as a helpful and supporting instrument rather than a hasty or shallow appraisal.

3.2.3. Requires Ample Time to prepare— One critical component of effective teaching is preparation and planning. If the teacher is behind in planning, then it will lead to failure. Good teachers are always overprepared, always thinking about the next lesson, and in a continuous state of preparation and planning. Preparation and planning should be viewed as investments, not as a waste of time. Such investments

matter and surely pay off. Angeles et al. (2023) noted that teachers must prepare for classroom observations in a number of ways. They must be ready to give their teachings effectively to the advantage of their students. The teachers were compelled to prepare their lessons better since they knew the pupils would receive them. They must have greater self-assurance while interacting with their co-teachers, who act as their students.

3.3. The Insights Drawn From The Teacher Performance Evaluation And Review In Increasing Time Management— During the in-depth interview, many themes and realizations emerged that were underpinned and unlocked. One realization was that insights could be generated into the teachers' apprehension of the classroom observation tools regarding

their activity alignment. In summary, by identifying areas for improvement and highlighting strengths, teacher performance reviews and evaluations help to produce well-prepared educators. Teachers receive thorough feedback that helps them understand the best practices and ideas for teaching that they may use in their classrooms. To address identified areas for improvement,

Fig. 4. Teachers Cope Up With Challenges In Acquiring Teacher Performance Evaluation And Review, Increasing Time Management

this strategy encourages instructors to participate in ongoing professional development activities, including workshops and training. Consequently, educators enhance their abilities, prepare more effective lessons, and modify their teaching strategies to suit the requirements of their students better. Teachers are incentivized

to remain current with educational trends and best practices due to the systematic nature of the review process. In general, performance reviews favor student learning by assisting teachers in becoming more self-assured and productive.

3.3.1. Well-prepared Teachers—In other words, teachers' preparedness in the educational system is one factor in the success of the teaching and learning process. Teachers must prepare beforehand to avoid cramming, stress, and burnout. Thus, well-prepared teachers should be considered for both the success of the teaching pedagogy and the student engagement in the teaching and learning process. In conclusion, based on the results above, by highlighting creative ways to instruction and classroom management, teacher performance assessments and evaluations can bring attention to the creativity of their teachers. Teachers can use these reviews as a platform to display their original lesson

ideas, inventive approaches to tackling problems, and captivating teaching techniques that improve student learning. Teachers who can creatively adjust their teaching methods to meet the demands of a varied student body might be recognized and commended by evaluators. When evaluations emphasize creativity, educators are inspired to try new things and think creatively. This acknowledgement encourages an innovative culture among the school community and raises teacher morale. In the end, assessments that emphasize innovative teaching techniques can result in more engaging and productive classroom environments that are advantageous to teachers and students.

3.3.2. Be Creative—Teachers primarily deliver instructions for the learner's sake as they are said to be the main clientele of the teaching and learning process. Teachers must be creative and innovative to provide instruction with respect to the multiple intelligences of the students and their varied learning styles. This is a win-win situation for both teachers and students. Students are primarily supplied with their learning needs using the creative differentiated instruction. At the same time, teachers practice their way of teaching by integrating multi-talented students with varied learning activities. Teacher performance reviews and evaluations provide specific feedback on instructional practices, which is essential for enhancing teaching

competence. Teachers can improve their strategies and tactics by using these evaluations to pinpoint their areas of strength and room for improvement. The procedure pushes educators to participate in professional development activities, like training sessions and workshops, to target areas that require improvement. Evaluations assist teachers in concentrating on learning new techniques and abilities that increase their efficacy in the classroom by establishing clear objectives and standards. Higher teaching standards result from this ongoing feedback loop, which encourages a culture of learning and self-improvement among educators. Enhancing one's teaching ability ultimately increases student engagement, comprehension, and academic success.

3.3.3. Enhanced Teaching Competence—

Fig. 5. The Insights Drawn From The Teacher Performance Evaluation And Review in Increasing Time Management

Classroom observation plays a central role in making teaching and learning more visible. It provides teachers constructive critical feedback to improve classroom management and instructional techniques. Teachers need to observe the interaction between teacher and learner within

the classroom because it can determine the learning opportunities students get. Classroom observation also encourages colleagues to collaborate to improve teacher practice and student learning.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions regarding teachers’ experiences of classroom observations as a tool for improving teaching skills were discussed.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to examine the educational possibilities for the synergy of continuous professional development of teachers by analyzing their experience, advantages and disadvantages, and insights on teacher performance evaluation and review. Two themes were obtained for Figure three as described by the Experiences of Teachers on the Increasing Time Management. Teachers

mentioned and revealed during the interview: Reduced teacher stress and improved teaching skills. Meanwhile, the fourth figure also possesses three themes that the teachers grasped as they described the coping strategies that they have come up with to manage the said apprehensions on the classroom observation tool as an avenue for the activity alignment. First was the openness to teachers’ critiques; next is the

promotion of teacher development; and finally, there was ample time to prepare for the classroom observation tool. Lastly, the educational insight of the teachers on the teacher evaluation

4.2. Implications—The interview conducted in this study revealed the teachers' experiences, coping strategies, and insights. Teacher evaluation was now a trend in the teaching process. It has been an aid to the teachers in enhancing the instructional process of the chosen field. The teachers' experiences with the teacher evaluation were evident in Figure Three. Teachers mentioned and revealed during the interview that reduced teacher stress and improved teaching skills were two things that they have chiefly experienced. This primarily connotes that teachers need time management to reduce the stress that they experience. Teacher undergoing evaluation was also an ace since this is performed by the teachers and evaluated by the highly experienced individuals or the said mentors, who were the ones to make feedback, suggestions, and clarifications that the teachers must abide by to achieve developed teaching skills fully. However, as teachers apprehend, mentor partnerships, and enhance teaching skills in classroom observations, they have also encountered stress and burnout throughout the classroom observation process due to prolonged and sleepless nights to prepare. Moreover, the teachers' apprehension about the classroom observation tool was highlighted, which made teachers prepare for it and come up with coping mechanisms. Moreover, the teachers' apprehension became a mirror of how effective the classroom observation tool was in the instructional process, as it mainly tracked the things that the teachers needed to modify and enhance in the said process. The fourth figure, with themes of open-mindedness of the teachers, was the promotion of teacher development. Finally, the ample time to prepare for the classroom obser-

exemplified three themes drawn and observed during the interview. These were the following: well-prepared teachers, enhanced teaching competence, and being more creative.

vation tool is accentuated. It was apparent that as the teachers were evaluated, they were given varied criticism, suggestions, and recommendations on polishing their teaching performance. One thing that teachers need to do is to embrace whatever evaluation that the highly experienced individual provides. This portrays the open-mindedness of the teachers to those criticisms and uses them as a stepping stone to achieve success in teaching, which will eventually promote teacher development. Moreover, the respondents also stressed that teachers avoid cramming and perform smoothly, and they cope by giving ample time to prepare. This is indeed a great help for the teachers to improve their way of delivering the instructional process as well as for the benefit of the students to perform well in the classroom activities. Finally, for the insights given by the teachers, they highlighted the stipulation of well-prepared teachers, enhanced teaching competence, and being more creative. With this theme, it is a reminder that along with the teaching pedagogy, teachers must be prepared most especially in the delivery of instruction, this is to ensure the effectiveness, as well as the success and enhancement of the teaching performance, as well as to satisfy the learners with the lesson. Lastly, the participants also give greater emphasis on being creative. This is very particular since we inculcate quality teaching to the students and want to produce responsible and independent learners that the society envisions to have. Thus, the department of education should take note of these matters and listen to the voice of the teachers because teachers were the forefront of all services and works of all programs offered by the department. They are the implementers who experience a lot

of positive and negative feedback from the parent and stakeholders. Sometimes, teachers were shock absorbers, so let us understand that they

made them happy and at ease by unloading them with lots of work.

4.3. Future Directions—Department of Education. Offering equipped training, workshops, seminars, and other essential programs to ensure teachers' welfare provides varied opportunities to unlock educational possibilities and continuously grow in their profession. Teachers. Acquiring a skillset from teacher performance evaluation and review can help them effectively build a solid foundation for their profession, continuously grow, and enhance and practice their teaching skillset to achieve improved teaching performances. Teacher performance review and evaluation may be crucial for improving teacher quality and time management. They provide feedback, identify areas for growth, and can lead to more effective teaching practices and better time allocation. School Principals. This instrument may help the school head de-

termine which aspect of teachers' performance needs to be updated or improved. Teacher performance review and evaluation systems, when implemented effectively, support school principals by providing data-driven insights into teacher performance, informing professional development, and ultimately contributing to improved student outcomes and a stronger school community. Future Researcher. Lastly, this study's findings will enable future researchers to facilitate research that involves teacher performance evaluation, which would help teachers improve their teaching and management. This study would also serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies. The results may also be published in a reputable journal so that others can access them as a basis for their references.

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